

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Project 'CarboSeq'

Deliverable D#-WP1.5

Final report of the CarboSeq project

Due date of deliverable: M58

Actual submission date: 11.01.2025

Final report of the CarboSeq project

EJP SOIL - CarboSeq
Deliverable D#-WP1.5

General Data

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: CarboSeq

Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D#-WP1.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE: Final report of the CarboSeq project
DELIVERABLE TYPE: Report
WORK PACKAGE: WP1
WORK PACKAGE TITLE: Coordination
DELIVERABLE LEADER: Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture, Germany
AUTHORS: Felix Seidel, Heide Spiegel, Alice Budai, Brieuc Hardy, Carlos Sierra, Cathal Buckley, Cesar Plaza, Chiara Piccini, Claudia Di Bene, Claudio Mondini, Daniel Rasse, Daria Seitz, Eugenio Diaz-Pines, Felix Herzog, Florent Levavasseur, Florian Schneider, Gianni Bellocchi, Greet Ruyschaert, Irene Criscuoli, Jan Peter Lesschen, Jens Leifeld, Jonathan Holland, Jorge Alvaro-Fuentes, Katharina Keiblinger, Katja Klumpp, Lars Elsgaard, Lauric Cecillon, Manuel Martin, Mariangela Diacono, Marjetka Suhadolc, Martin Bolinder, Oyinlola Ogunpaimo, Roberta Farina, Silvia Vanino, Simon Weldon, Thomas Kätterer, Valerie Viaud, Axel Don
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14631501
LICENSE CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL: CO/PU

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge all the people who contributed to this report.

Name	Institute
Dario Fornara	AFBI
Jonathan Holland	AFBI
Michelle Allen	AFBI
Felix Herzog	Agroscope
Jens Leifeld	Agroscope
Juliane Hirte	Agroscope
leonormaria.gondimrodrigues	Agroscope
Sonja Keel	Agroscope
Sonja Kay	Agroscope
Borut Vrščaj	AIS
Dencso Marton	ATK
Eszter Tóth	ATK
Márton Dencső	ATK
Zsófia Bakacsi	ATK
Arezo Taghizadeh-Toosi	AU
Lars Elsgaard	AU
Cecilie Foldal	BFW
Robert Jandl	BFW
Heide Spiegel	BIOS-AGES
Sophia Goetzinger	BIOS-AGES
Taru Sanden	BIOS-AGES
Eugenio Diaz-Pines	BIOS-BOKU
Katharina Keiblinger	BIOS-BOKU
Ulises Esparza-Robles	BIOS-BOKU
Brieuc Hardy	CRAW
Bruno Huyghebaert	CRA-W
Frédéric Vanwindekens	CRA-W
Chiara Piccini	CREA
Claudia Di Bene	CREA
Claudio Mondini	CREA
Francesco Galioto	CREA
Giovanni Daraguccione	CREA
Irene Criscuoli	CREA
Mariangela Diacono	CREA
Roberta Farina	CREA
Silvia Vanino	CREA
César Plaza	CSIC
Jorge Álvaro-Fuentes	CSIC
Laura Martinez	CSIC
María Alonso	CSIC
Pablo García-Palacios	CSIC
Ivana Galušková	CZU
Radim Vašát	CZU
Tereza Zádorová	CZU
Vít Penížel	CZU
Ladislav Menšík	CZU - subcontracting VÚVR

Name	Institute
Bert Reubens	EV-ILVO
Greet Ruyschaert	EV-ILVO
Guillaume Blanchy	EV-ILVO
Ioanna Panagea	EV-ILVO
Kaat Mertens	EV-ILVO
Katrien Oorts	EV-ILVO
Maarten De Boever	EV-ILVO
Miro Jacob	EV-ILVO
Paul Pardon	EV-ILVO
Peter Maenhout	EV-ILVO
Sofie Annys	EV-ILVO
Tommy D'Hose	EV-ILVO
Jose A Rodriguez	INIA
Jose L Gabriel	INIA
Maria M Delgado	INIA
Ana Marta Paz	INIAV
Corina Carranca	INIAV
Inés Santín Montanyá	INIAV
Maria Gonçalves	INIAV
Nadia Castanheira	INIAV
Raquel Mano	INIAV
Anne-Isabelle Graux	INRAE
Antonio Bispo	INRAE
Eric Casellas	INRAE
Fabien Ferchaud	INRAE
Florent Levavasseur	INRAE
Gianni Bellocchi	INRAE
Hélène Raynal	INRAE
Julien Wengler	INRAE
Katja Klumpp	INRAE
Lauric Cécillon	INRAE
Manuel Martin	INRAE
Patrick Chabrier	INRAE
Rachid Yahiaoui	INRAE
Raphaël Martin	INRAE
Sabine Houot	INRAE
Valerie Viaud	INRAE
Grzegorz Siebielec	IUNG
Ieva Mockeviciene	LAMMC
Monika Vilkiene	LAMMC
Alice Budai	NIBIO
Christophe Moni	NIBIO
Daniel Rasse	NIBIO
Simon Weldon	NIBIO
Teresa G. Bárcena	NIBIO
Gabriela Barancikova	NPPC
Jan Halas	NPPC
Rastislav Skalský	NPPC
Stefan Koco	NPPC

Name	Institute
Benjamin Bukombe	SLU
Carlos Sierra	SLU
Lorenzo Menichetti	SLU
Martin Bolinder	SLU
Nargish Parvin	SLU
Rong Lang	SLU
Thomas Kätterer	SLU
Atila Polat	TAGEM
Emre Can Kaya	TAGEM
İsmail Çinkaya	TAGEM
Mehmet Gur	TAGEM
Muhammed Halil Koparan	TAGEM
Nejat Özden	TAGEM
Sevinc Madenoglu	TAGEM
Ülfet Erdal	TAGEM
Zeynep Demir	TAGEM
Cathal Buckley	Teagasc
David Wall	Teagasc
Gary Lanigan	Teagasc
Oyinlola Ogunpaimo	Teagasc
Anna Jacobs	Thünen
Axel Don	Thünen
Daria Seitz	Thünen
Dave Emde	Thünen
Florian Schneider	Thünen
Neha Begill	Thünen
Sophie Drexler	Thünen
Kristina Ocvirk	ULBF
Marjetka Suhadolc	ULBF
Rok Mihelič	ULBF
Denis Stajnko	UM-FKBV
Chantal Hendriks	WR
Jan Peter Lesschen	WR
Rima Porre	WR
Thalisa Slier	WR
Fulu Tao	LUKE
Alar Astover	EMU
Karin Kauer	EMU

Executive summary

Soil and land degradation threatens agricultural production, soil health and undermines efforts to sequester carbon in soils in order to combat climate change. The adoption of sustainable agricultural management ensures the provision of ecosystem services and could enhance soil functions. Soil functions are positively affected by carbon content, thus increasing carbon stocks in soils is desired and even considered as a mean to make agriculture more environmentally sustainable and climate friendly. Studies on the effect of agricultural management options on soil organic carbon became popular particularly focusing to mitigate climate change effects. Yet, so far only few studies tried to quantify the carbon sequestration potential of different measures beyond a theoretical potential. This project fills this gap and determines a feasible carbon sequestration potential of ten agricultural measures with two approaches: 1. Based on novel emission factors and an area of additional implementation across Europe, including of N₂O emission changes and subsoil C changes. 2. Additionally, the soil carbon model RothC has been applied to European and national datasets estimating the carbon sequestration potential in a modelling approach.

It was found in the emission factor approach, that if all the measures were fully implemented, the equivalent of up to one-fifth of current agricultural greenhouse gas emissions (including LULUCF) of the EU, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey could be avoided annually. Biochar application showed the highest potential for soil carbon accrual accounting for around 60% of the total potential followed by agroforestry measures. Non-inversion or no-tillage, fodder legume and ley rotations, as well as cover crops show intermediate potentials. Optimized crop residue management and irrigation are limited in their carbon sequestration potential by the availability of additional residues and infrastructure. Overall, agroforestry systems showed the highest potential carbon sequestration efficiency per hectare due to their additional C sequestration in biomass. The cost-effective measures at the EU scale were the agroforestry measures at a shadow price of carbon of 89 € per Mg CO₂e⁻¹.

In the modelling approach, three agricultural management options have been modelled, namely optimized residue management, improved cover crop implementation and increased ley rotations. It was found at the European scale that the improvement of crop residues management on arable land could potentially lead to a C accrual of 0.14 Mg C ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ on average and a total of 53 Mio Mg CO₂e⁻¹ at EU scale. Further, a wider implementation of cover crops would allow an average C accrual of 0.58 Mg C ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ and a total of 224 Mio Mg CO₂e⁻¹ at EU scale. However, the modelling exercise demonstrated that the confidence in the proposed results is medium to low, as there are multiple issues with data availability, quality and quantity.

It is important to consider site specific effects of each measure concerning trade-offs and co-benefits to ensure sustainable soil management. The success of carbon sequestration efforts in European agriculture hinges on scaling up the area where agricultural measures are implemented, with economic incentives playing a crucial role in turning potential sequestration into realized outcomes.

Table of contents

General Data	3
Acknowledgements	5
Executive summary	8
What is CarboSeq about?	10
Scientific findings of the project	11
Component A.....	13
Zero tillage and non-inversion tillage.....	13
Irrigation	14
Perennial legumes and temporary ley management	14
Cover crops.....	15
Crop residues management	15
Agroforestry	16
Biochar and other amendments.....	16
Optimized grassland management.....	17
Summary component A.....	19
Component B.....	19
Non-CO ₂ Greenhouse gases	19
Subsoils.....	20
Waterlogged mineral soils.....	21
Component C.....	21
Area of implementation	22
Estimation of the C sequestration potential	24
Roth C EU model runs.....	26
National model runs of RothC.....	27
Comparison of RothC with other models.....	28
Root-Shoot database.....	28
Economical evaluation of the measures	29
Key results and research gaps	29
Publications linked to CarboSeq	31
Data sets and tools linked to CarboSeq	33
Selected meaningful deliverables linked to CarboSeq	34
References	35

What is CarboSeq about?

The EJP SOIL CarboSeq project is a research project under the broader European Joint Programme for Soil (EJP SOIL), which focuses on enhancing sustainable soil management practices, particularly in relation to carbon sequestration in Europe (Figure 1).

Soil and land degradation pose serious challenges to our societies, contributing to climate change, biodiversity loss, and declines in agricultural production (Keesstra et al., 2024). However, well-managed or restored soils are also viewed as a crucial part of the solution, capable of providing vital ecosystem services. Land use and management of agricultural systems have been known to affect the soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks through changes in land use, cropping practices (intensity and types of crops), irrigation, fertilization, tillage, and other management activities (Panagea et al., 2023). Consequently, land use and land management can potentially be used to reduce greenhouse gas emissions or even

Figure 1: Countries assessed by the CarboSeq project for their carbon sequestration potentials (green). Red countries are not evaluated.

sequester carbon (C) by promoting practices that increase C input to the soil, thus, increasing carbon dioxide (CO₂) removal from the atmosphere and incorporation in the soil. The "4 per 1000" Initiative, launched at the COP21 climate summit in Paris in 2015, determined that by a global increase of soil C stocks by 0.4% (or 4 per 1000) annually, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions could be offset and food security could be significantly increased (Minasny et al., 2017). However, this 0.4% increase includes all soils worldwide, not just managed soils such as those under agricultural use and is thus just a theoretical construct to visualize the importance of soil carbon in the global carbon cycle. The amount of C that can be additionally stored in soils through practices that increase soil C remains unclear while policy makers and other stakeholders envision soils to be one of the measures for climate change mitigation. Thus, there is an urgent need of a better quantification of the potential of agricultural soils as C sinks if the EU is to fulfil the European Green Deal's promise and achieve climate neutrality by 2050 (Fetting, 2020).

This is why the CarboSeq project specifically aimed at investigating and identifying farming and land management practices that can effectively capture and store more C in soils and to quantify these increases across European agricultural systems to mitigate climate change effects. Thus, in order to come from theoretical potentials to feasible potentials, C sequestration was linked with management options that also account for the biophysical and technical constraints for the implementation of these options. The project was a collaboration of 26 European partner institutions. For this, a database has been created including over 450 European (long- and mid-term) experiments from which agricultural measures have been identified that reliably and proven in practice increase SOC. New European emission factors have been calculated for cropland and grassland management options. In addition,

biochar and other soil amendments have been studied to determine their C sequestration potentials. Furthermore, the project studied emissions of other non-CO₂ GHGs to assess the impact of changes in agricultural management practices on overall GHG emissions, factoring in the C accrual shifts. The project went even further and studied the importance of subsoils and waterlogged soils in the context of climate change mitigation and the consequences for soil monitoring. Building on this work, tools like the soil carbon model RothC and other methodologies such as management related emission factors have been refined and enhanced to provide more accurate estimates of potential C sequestration in Europe. These improvements are crucial for establishing more reliable systems for C accounting. Using these improved methods, the C sequestration potential of European agricultural soils has been estimated, assuming broader implementation of the identified agricultural practices. These estimates have been contextualized within the framework of Europe's climate goals, highlighting their contribution to achieving those targets, and those of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). As a result, the project offers robust scientific evidence to inform and support policymakers on matters related to potentials of C sequestration in European agricultural soils and how these could contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal.

Scientific findings of the project

This report contains key results of CarboSeq and is divided into three parts following the structure of the project (Figure 2). The first part presents findings and results related to identifying and quantifying the effects of agricultural management options that increase C accrual in croplands and grasslands to help minimise C losses or even allow for C sequestration. Additionally, it covers research on biochar and other amendments that contribute to increasing SOC as well (Component A). The second part covers uncertainties (Component B), specifically the effect of non-CO₂ GHG emissions linked to agricultural management changes, the importance of subsoils for soil C quantification and waterlogging. In the third part, the C sequestration potential throughout Europe is presented and discussed using two approaches: emission factors and modelling.

Figure 2: Project structure with three components (management options, uncertainties and modelling) containing different work packages (WP)

Component A

Component A focused on identifying and evaluating agricultural management options for their C sequestration potentials in croplands and grasslands including measures that may increase C stability through carbonisation, composting, and fermentation of crop residues and liming. The two main goals of component A were to estimate SOC stock changes (emission factors) and C-input changes, using IPCC-Tier 2 for broad estimates and Tier 3 for higher spatial resolution on the one hand. On the other hand, to identify potential barriers, costs, and benefits of these measures, aiding component C in evaluating the feasibility of agricultural management options that increase the C accrual in European agricultural soils.

To evaluate the effect of cropland management options, a database was created with European data from over 450 long- and mid-term field experiments (LTEs & MTEs) (Ruyschaert et al., 2023) enabling the identification of ten agricultural management options reliably increasing C accrual and to quantify this increase expressed as emission factors (EFs) (Panagea et al., 2023; Leifeld et al., 2024a; Klumpp and Holland, 2024). These options included technical solutions (zero tillage, non-inversion tillage, irrigation, biochar application), optimized crop rotations (perennial legumes and temporary ley management, cover crops, crop residues management), and agroforestry (hedgerows, alley cropping, silvopasture). Each measure was then clearly defined (Seidel et al., 2024). Subsequently, estimation of robust and representative EFs was attempted which can only be achieved through analysis of carefully compiled measured data from LTEs. Thus, through the database, estimates of the different EFs for each management option were derived alongside significant pedoclimatic and management predictors for each option and are described in detail in Panagea et al. (2023).

Zero tillage and non-inversion tillage

We derived EFs for non-inversion tillage (minimum or non-inversion tillage) and zero tillage (no tillage, the absence of mechanical soil disturbance) practices based on European LTEs (min. duration 5 years) by comparing these management options to conventional inversion tillage (ploughing) to disentangle the main factors that determine the relative EFs in the 0 to 30 cm soil layer. It was impossible to include deeper soil layers due to the lack of available data.

For the comparison between 'inversion tillage' and 'non-inversion tillage', selection resulted in 46 experiments, whereas for the comparison between 'inversion tillage' and 'zero-tillage', selection resulted in 27 different experiments. The mean duration of experiments on tillage practices was around 15 years. Zero-tillage trials were most common in Mediterranean climates (14 out of 27) and less frequent in Continental, Atlantic, Boreal, and Pannonian climates (Panagea et al., 2023). Non-inversion tillage was primarily studied in Continental climates (25 out of 46), with fewer experiments in Mediterranean, Atlantic, and Boreal climates. Only one zero-tillage experiment occurred in a Pannonian climate, and none for non-inversion tillage. Clay content in both tillage practices varied widely, with most experiments on loam and silty loam soils. Specifically, zero-tillage had 7 loam and 5 silty loam experiments (out of 27), while non-inversion tillage had 11 loam and 12 silty loam experiments (out of 47). No sandy soils were represented in the dataset.

Our analysis showed that for zero tillage, EF is 1.11 (SD \pm 0.19) using the equivalent soil mass approach. For non-inversion tillage, the EF is 1.03 (SD \pm 0.12) when considering equivalent soil mass. This meta-analysis across European croplands showed that both zero and non-inversion tillage have a C

sequestration potential, with zero tillage generally yielding higher EFs. Climate bias in the dataset, especially from semiarid Mediterranean regions, influenced results, yet EFs aligned with global IPCC estimates (1.1 for zero tillage, 1.05 for reduced tillage, (IPCC, 2019)). Soil type and sampling depth were key but marginal predictors of EF. Expanding data to more climates and soil textures could improve accuracy. Both measures are however, significantly enhancing SOC across Europe except in the boreal zone.

Irrigation

Until now, two published reviews have explored the impact of irrigation on SOC stocks (Trost et al., 2013; Emde et al., 2021). On the one hand, Trost et al. (2013) collected data from 14 LTEs (> 8 years) and analysed the SOC stocks under irrigation compared with non-irrigation. Only two of them were conducted in Europe (in Germany and Austria), with a duration of 32 and 27 years respectively. Emde et al. (2021) performed a meta-analysis of data from studies that examined changes in SOC stocks on irrigated agricultural sites over time.

Thus, it was expected to further search in literature and compile and analyse the results of European LTEs (>5 years) that investigate the impact of irrigation on arable land vs no irrigation on SOC stocks.

This resulted in the identification of eight experiments. From these, it was checked if they had SOC stock measurements for a depth of at least 10 cm. Only three experiments eventually qualified with one located in Germany, one in Austria and one in Italy. The EFs of these were 1.027 (SE \pm 0.006), 0.95 (SE \pm 0.011) and 0.90 (SE \pm 0.02) respectively (Panagea et al., 2023). Thus, irrigation showed a positive impact on SOC stocks only in one of the experiments performed under a dry-sub humid continental climate, whereas it led to SOC stock losses under a semiarid Mediterranean climate. Thus, there is not enough information to draw European specific conclusions about the impact of irrigation on soil SOC stocks. Therefore, more field experiments would be necessary to fill this gap. Based on the current European field evidence, we could not develop meaningful EFs and thus used the global value of 1.059 developed by Emde et al. (2021).

Perennial legumes and temporary ley management

In the “Crops and Crop Diversification” task it was assessed how changes in crop types as part of crop rotations impact SOC stocks, using data from the CarboSeq LTE database. Treatments were categorized by increased shares of legumes, cereals, root crops, monoculture versus rotation, and rotations with or without temporary leys. Categories for further analysis were selected based on their SOC increase potential, data availability, and relevance to EU policy goals (COM, 2020). Notably, increasing the share of legumes in rotations showed high potential for SOC enhancement and aligns with EU priorities on enhancing European legume protein production, thus warranting in-depth analysis.

A dataset from the CarboSeq database on increasing legumes in rotations was extracted, containing 32 experiments with 72 control-treatment pairs (Panagea et al., 2023). Only forage legumes were found to increase SOC and yield positive EFs, while grain legumes did not, leading to the exclusion of 28 grain legume pairs. The final dataset for analysis includes 21 experiments across 9 countries, totalling 39 control-treatment pairs: Italy (9), Spain (7), Czech Republic (5), Denmark (5), Germany (4), Norway (3), Sweden (3), Belgium (2), and Lithuania (1).

The observed relative EFs of the forage legumes ranged between 0.74-1.89 with the average value among all observations to be 1.08 (SE \pm 0.03, SD \pm 0.21). After testing for effects of climate and soil variables, the final EF takes the following form:

$$EF = 1.182198 + 0.003957 * \text{percentage difference (\%)} - 0.129105 * \text{SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1})$$

where “percentage difference” refers to additional fraction of fodder legumes in the rotation (%) compared to the control treatment. Climate effects could not be taken into account linked to an unbalanced distribution of LTE’s across Europe (Panagea et al., 2025, under review).

Cover crops

The long-term C sequestration potential by growing cover crops versus no cover crops in European agro-ecosystems was analysed by extracting data from the CarboSeq LTE database (Ruysschaert et al., 2023). The selected dataset follows key criteria: (1) the only difference between control and treatment is cover crop cultivation, with other factors constant; (2) cover crops are included in at least 50% of the rotation; (3) data is from annual cropping systems; and (4) experiments run for at least five years.

This yielded 13 experiments with 27 control-treatment pairs, spanning from southern Sweden to central Spain, primarily within continental and Atlantic climate zones. The average experiment duration was 11.3 years, with soil sampling typically to a depth of at least 20 cm. Thirteen experiments used single cover crops species, and 14 used mixtures, primarily featuring ryegrass, winter vetch, radish, oat, and mustard. Inorganic fertilizers were used in 18 studies, while organic fertilizers were used in seven.

Overall, the mean relative EF across all observations was 1.06 (SE= \pm 0.02, SD= \pm 0.08). The estimated EF aligns well with previous studies (e.g. Poeplau and Don, 2015). However, climatic factors appear to be stronger predictors of relative EFs than soil type or management practices across Europe. The dataset was limited, with LTEs focusing solely on cover cropping and a biased spatial distribution, particularly underrepresenting Boreal and Mediterranean climates and while loamy soil types were over represented. Due to these limitations and a lack of significant differences between climate zones, a single EF of 1.06 (\pm 0.02) is recommended for cover crops across Europe until further evidence becomes available.

Crop residues management

The long-term carbon sequestration potential of retaining versus completely removing crop residues in European agro-ecosystems was assessed. Experiments over Europe were chosen from the CarboSeq LTE database (Ruysschaert et al., 2023) that compare treatments where crop residues had been removed against those where crop residues had been retained and incorporated, for at least consecutive 5 years.

A total of 38 experiments was extracted and analysed with crop residues originating from cereals (e.g. spring wheat, winter wheat, spring barley, winter barley, winter rye, maize/corn, triticale and oats) and other crops (e.g. lupines, rapeseed, clover, sugar beet, pea, sunflower, beans (soy, broad, horse, field, faba), potato, mustard (white, yellow, oilseed), winter oil radish, vetch, ryegrass and sorghum).

The average experiment duration was 29.5 (SD +/- 14.3) years, with soil sampling to an average depth of 23.5 cm.

The mean EF for retained crop residues was 1.09 (SD +/- 0.12, SE +/- 0.02). After further testing a more accurate estimation could be proposed:

$$EF = 1.114560 - 0.075746 * SOC \text{ of the control per cm (Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) + 0.214673 * \text{crop rotation (decimal)} + 0.002988 * \text{Clay content (\%)} - 0.000147 * \text{annual rainfall (mm)}$$

With crop rotation (decimal) representing the fraction of cereals included in the crop rotation.

Agroforestry

The task study aimed to assess the impact of agroforestry systems on SOC stocks, using data from European field observations. It specifically compared SOC levels in areas affected by existing tree lines with those in field locations unaffected by tree line influence.

The dataset for the analysis includes 6 experiments located in 4 different countries and 3 different climatic zones with 17 pairs of treatments and control (i.e., 12 in Belgium, 3 in France, 1 in United Kingdom, 1 in Switzerland) and was extracted from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (Ruysschaert et al., 2023). 12 pairs focus on hedge systems, another 5 pairs on alley-cropping in or around cropland.

The relative emission factors (EFs) for all systems, including hedgerows and alley-cropping tree strips, ranged from 0.91 to 1.81, with an average of 1.26 (SD ±0.21, SE ±0.05). There were differences between hedge and alley-cropping systems, with average EFs of 1.29 (SD ±0.23, SE ±0.06) for hedgerows and 1.19 (SD ±0.09, SE ±0.01) for alley-cropping. However, these differences were not statistically significant due to the limited data available. The sample size is too small and unbalanced (4 alley-cropping, 13 hedgerows; 13 Atlantic, 2 Mediterranean, 2 Continental), making it unreliable for assessing the effects of climate, soil variables, or system-related factors (such as system age and tree species). Furthermore, for silvopasture, no sufficient data could be identified, thus no change in SOC is assumed following Drexler et al. (2021).

We suggest using the same EF value for both – hedgerow and alley cropping systems – of 1.26 (SD: ±0.21, SE: ±0.05). The value represents exclusively the area covered with woody elements, i.e., either the area of the tree strip in alley-cropping systems or the area covered by hedges.

Biochar and other amendments

Stabilizing organic materials via aerobic or anaerobic decomposition (i.e., composting or fermentation) or pyrolysis to biochar comes at the expense of reducing the C bound in the material for eventual conversion to SOM (Leifeld et al., 2024a). Different pathways of plant biomass use were compared (compost, digestate, manure, farmyard manure, slurry, sewage sludge, biochar) regarding their long-term effect on SOC stocks.

A new version of RothC (Keel et al., 2023) has been developed where two exogenous organic matter (EOM) pools have been added, one fast and one slow decomposing pool, based on 56 EOM types. This new approach can simulate the long-term effect of EOM addition on SOC stocks, with RothC being a well-established model for such studies. However, no universal EOM emission factor is suggested, as

the effect of EOM addition depends on application rates and site conditions (e.g., climate, soil properties, and management). The improved parameterization of RothC is recommended for evaluating EOM addition in terms of soil carbon storage (Leifeld et al., 2024b). Further, the effect of soil pH and liming on SOC stocks has been evaluated and there was no strong and systematic evidence of a net effect of liming on SOC stocks in agricultural soils. Therefore, a pH response function was not implemented into RothC (Leifeld et al., 2024a).

Using this new approach, the amendments contribution to increasing SOC stocks has been evaluated. The simulations showed that after approximately three decades of annual EOM application, SOC stocks appear to reach a new steady state for all EOMs, except biochar. This is attributed to biochar's high stability, with its labile fraction averaging less than 2%. SOC increases compared to baseline levels were highest after biochar addition, followed by digestate, compost, and animal manure, with plant material showing the smallest increase, when adding the same amount of carbon. When related to the initial C in the plant material before processing, however, plant material outperformed the EOMs except biochar. We conclude that the trade-off between off-site stabilization and in-soil mineralization does not undermine the use of biochar for soil carbon storage. Despite the high carbon losses (about 50%) during biochar production, more carbon remains in the soil due to its very low decomposition rates. In terms of carbon sequestration efficiency, biochar outperforms other biomass processing methods.

Thus, biochar seems to be the most promising method when aiming at long-term increases of SOC stocks. Its decomposability is strongly determined by its physico-chemical properties, which themselves are mainly a function of i) the feedstock and ii) the pyrolysis conditions. We found that the biochar's H/C_{org} ratio can serve as a reliable indicator of biochar stability. It is therefore suggested to use that indicator for biochar classification in the context of long-term stability in soil (Leifeld et al., 2024a). As the long-term sequestration induced by adding biochar primarily depends on the biochar's stability as well as on the C yield of pyrolysis, combining these two properties gives C emission factors. We define a 100-years C emission factor for biochar addition as:

$$EF_{biochar100} = F_{perm} \times C_{yield}$$

where C_{yield} is the C yield of the pyrolysis. This way of calculation equals the term 'carbon sequestration efficiency' as shown by Rodrigues et al.,(2023) and takes into account i) C losses from the initial processing (here: pyrolysis) and ii) a calculated time-horizon of 100 years, following the F_{perm} concept of (IPCC, 2019).

Optimized grassland management

A database containing 465 data records across 63 studies (mostly long-term experiments) in 8 different European countries has been created to evaluate management effects on SOC stocks in European grasslands. The exploration of this database showed that the most common management treatments involved the application of known quantities of inorganic or organic fertilizers, but few studies provided details on other practices. Information on mowing intensity, grazing, lime applications, soil tillage, and reseeded was rarely included, and there were no studies on irrigation treatments. Species diversity and plant functional group data were only available in a small number of studies. The most common land use treatments were defined based on whether the treatment and control were identical, including pastures, moors, heathland, or natural grassland. Land use studies were

categorized into several groups, such as crop/arable land, agroforestry and silvopastoral land, and forest or woodland.

Emission factors (EFs) were calculated from long-term grassland experiments in seven European countries (Table 1). The overall mean EF for value for LTEs was 1.15.

Table 1: . Summary of the simulated mean emission factor values (EFs) values for selected land use and management measures from long-term grassland experiments in Europe. From: (Holland et al., 2024b)

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	197	1.16	0.02	0.60
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	61	1.14	0.05	
2 ^a	Arable control	19	0.96	0.04	0.001
2 ^a	Grass	17	1.37	0.11	
2 ^a	Agroforestry	21 (one experiment)	1.19	0.07	
2 ^a	Wood	3	0.77	0.08	
3 ^b	Remaining Grass (Control)	9	1.13	0.03	0.015
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	175	1.14	0.02	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	1.34	0.03	

The mean annual SOC stock change rate (t C/ha/yr) was 0.25 (± 0.03) for grassland nutrient management, 0.14 (± 0.24) for land use change from crop to grassland, 0.01 (± 0.32) for LUC grassland integrating silvo-pastoral, and 0.24 (± 0.06) for LUC from crop to agroforestry including grassland. For grassland with nutrient management the net SOC stock change decreased with rainfall, but increased with mineral fertilization (according to an increase of 1 kg C/ha/yr for each 2.7 kg of applied N).

Simulation with RothC showed better simulation results for remaining grasslands and land management than for LUC treatments. The plant C inputs needed to attain a positive SOC stock change were on average 2.97 t C/ ha/ yr (± 0.1) for management practices and 3.16 (± 0.3) for different land use types. Among LUC C inputs were 2.51 (± 0.28); 2.5 (± 0.13) and 3.3 (± 0.6) t C/ ha/ yr for LUC to agroforestry with grass, crop to grasslands and silvo-pastoral area. For nutrient management the plant C inputs were 2.86 (± 0.11) and 4.11 (± 0.23) t C/ ha/ yr for improved mineral fertilisation and organic fertilisation. The estimated plant C inputs varied between soil types, increased with rainfall and decreased with mean annual temperature, which partially explained the differences between countries. Due to the relatively low number of LTE data (n = 298) that were suitable for RothC simulation there was a need for alternative methods to improving understanding on plant C inputs across European grasslands. From the LUCAS data we calculated an annual soil C stock change of + 1.13 t C / ha/ yr. Applying the RothC simulation methodology for the LUCAS data we estimated the mean plant C inputs was 6.82 t C ha⁻¹ (SE ± 0.16) for European grasslands varying from 3.0 to 8.7 t C ha⁻¹. Simulated plant C inputs increased with rainfall and clay content.

Summary component A

Component A created databases from which agricultural measures were identified that lead to increased C stocks in European agricultural soils, including technical solutions (tillage practices, irrigation, biochar application), optimized crop rotations (perennial legumes and temporary ley management, cover crops, crop residues management), and agroforestry (Ruyschaert et al., 2023; Holland et al., 2024a). Grassland measures were not taken further into account due to the limited amount of available data and thus high uncertainty. Each measure has been clearly defined (Seidel et al., 2024), and new European emission factors could be estimated for all measures, except for irrigation (Panagea et al., 2023; Leifeld et al., 2024a).

Component B

Component B focused on key factors for uncertainties related to estimation of C sequestration potentials or total climate impact of agricultural measures with the aspects of non-CO₂ GHGs, subsoil SOC and water-logged mineral soils. These three aspects have been assessed through creation and analysis of data bases and literature reviews. The analysis focused on the agricultural management options identified in component A but is not limited to those. In addition, based on the results it was evaluated how to improve SOC modelling with RothC regarding these uncertainties.

Non-CO₂ Greenhouse gases

Other GHG emissions related to C sequestration in soils measures might reduce or increase the mitigation potential of agricultural management options. Especially nitrous oxide (N₂O) might have the risk to increase when measures are taken that increase SOC stocks, as SOC is one of the controlling factors for N₂O emissions (Nikolaus and Lesschen, 2024). This risk is especially relevant in the long term, if N₂O emissions remain, while the effect of potential C sequestration is becoming less due to reaching a new equilibrium in the soil. Some model studies (Li et al., 2005; Lugato et al., 2018) have shown that this might reduce or even completely off-set the mitigation potential of C sequestration efforts. Besides N₂O emissions, also potential trade-offs or co-benefits of other GHG emissions were assessed, to come up with a more complete evaluation of the climate mitigation effects of the agricultural management options identified by component A.

A database has been created together with the EJP SOIL WP7.3 and work packages that contains 243 experiments with necessary soil, climate and management data in order to evaluate the effect of the identified agricultural management options that increase SOC stocks (Blanchy et al., 2023). With the help of this database, the Impacts of N₂O soil emissions has been analysed in a literature review by (Porre et al., 2026, in prep.). The exploration of available data from European LTEs showed that not all management options identified by component A could be investigated for potential trade-offs of C sequestration. The following practices could be analysed: no- and reduced tillage, agroforestry, a change in crop rotation, cover crops, leaving crop residues on the field, land use change to energy crops (willow and miscanthus), and land use change cropland to grassland.

Additionally, the literature was searched to find and which farm operations change when a certain measure is applied in order to estimate changes in other GHG emissions. This included machinery use,

production of products such as fertilizers or pesticides, and the indirect emissions related to the fertilizer application. All emissions were recorded including consumption of fuel, electricity, or linked to a product. Here, the direct and indirect N₂O soil emissions, the emission factors from the IPCC were applied.

When comparing the average GHG emissions per baseline farm when including all abovementioned changes, land use change to miscanthus resulted in the highest emission reduction (more than 4 times lower emissions), followed by willow (almost twice as low). For both, the high reduction is primarily due to reduced fossil energy use from their bioenergy production. Adding legumes to crop rotations reduced emissions by 42%, mainly due to decreased fertilizer need, while agroforestry also reduced emissions by 19%, with fertilizer reduction playing a key role. Cover crops decreased NO₃ leaching, leading to a 5.4% reduction in emissions through this. N₂O emissions may increase through implementation of cover crops, but will not overcompensate the overall reduction in GHGs. Zero tillage and non-inversion tillage had minor reductions (2.8% and 2.2%, respectively). Conversely, land use change to grassland increased emissions (12%) due to higher fertilizer use, and leaving straw on the field raised emissions by 37% due to the loss of bioenergy production from straw. Considering food production and land use change, agroforestry offered the most benefits, as it could increase crop yields under specific conditions while reducing emissions. However, when C sequestration in soils is factored in, land use change to miscanthus ranks highest for reducing overall emissions, followed by willow, cover crops, crop rotation, no till, agroforestry, grassland, and non-inversion tillage, with crop residue incorporation increasing emissions compared to the baseline in which residues are used to substitute fossil fuels.

When accounting for changes in N₂O emissions and other trade-offs, the management options identified in component A (excluding biochar and irrigation) still demonstrate a potential for C sequestration, with any potential increases in N₂O emissions not outweighing the potential C sequestration benefits. For biochar a recent meta-analysis taking 8 studies into account demonstrated that its application to soils reduces N₂O emissions on average by 35% (Valkama et al., 2024) while there is no data on the effect of irrigation.

Subsoils

Subsoil (30–100 cm depth) stores similar amounts SOC as the topsoil arable layer (Morari et al., 2019). Yet, most studies on agroecosystem management options focus only on the topsoil layer where C cycling is more dynamic (Bolinder et al., 2020). Despite this, evidence from LTEs shows that common management practices can impact SOC stocks even in subsoil over decadal timescales, though the effect varies by site (e.g. Kätterer et al., 2014; Menichetti et al., 2015; Börjesson et al., 2018). Including subsoil layers in assessments is important, especially when comparing tillage practices, crop types (annual vs. perennial with deep roots), or major land-use changes (e.g., cropland to grassland or forest). While subsoil responses are site-specific, this area remains understudied (Lorenz and Lal, 2005; Chenu et al., 2019), highlighting a significant knowledge gap in SOC accounting. Given the small changes in C relative to total SOC stocks, LTEs are essential for accurately measuring the net impact of management options on subsoil C. This knowledge gap has been tackled in CarboSeq through literature review and compilation of LTE data on subsoil C in European agroecosystems. Specifically, subsoil SOC stock change rates were quantified and the influence of soil and climate factors has been assessed.

Finally, through synthesis of soil C models that capture subsoil dynamics, their sensitivity to stabilization changes at depth was evaluated.

The meta-analysis concluded that between 20-40% of SOC increases remains unaccounted for if subsoils are not considered (Parvin et al., 2024). Further, the key contributors to C sequestration in the subsoil were identified (Sierra et al., 2024). These contributors to soil C profiles include bioturbation, liquid phase transport, belowground C inputs, mineral associations, and microbial activity. Advective and diffusive transport play secondary roles, while the balance between vertical root inputs and decomposition primarily shapes C profiles. Only small amounts of new C inputs are stabilized in the long term (beyond 50 years), suggesting that subsoil C sequestration efforts must account for the limited stabilization of new inputs over extended periods.

An effort to improve the RothC model to consider subsoil C changes was made. The RothC model version presented by Jenkinson & Coleman (Jenkinson and Coleman, 2008) could be easily adapted to project SOC changes in subsoil. Based on the results from Sierra et al., (2024), the advection parameter should be very low. However, when including subsoil response, we also have to consider the negative response on SOC in no-till experiments (Meurer et al., 2018). It could not be resolved how RothC could be adapted to this during the project.

Waterlogged mineral soils

In water logged mineral soils C dynamics are much more influenced by the water regime as in well drained mineral soils. Water logged mineral soils are gleysols, fluvisols and others and are frequently used in agriculture mainly as grassland but also as croplands. Carbon models such as RothC are only calibrated and validated for well drained soils and thus there is little knowledge on how agricultural measures for C sequestration affect SOC stocks of waterlogged mineral soils. The aim was to fill this gap and compile existing data and knowledge. The task had to focus on few Irish flux tower sites since other LTEs were not available. Results in this task are thus only underlining the need for further field studies on the effect of waterlogging on SOC dynamics.

Component C

Component C focused on quantifying C sequestration potential across Europe, grounded in realistic, feasible assumptions constrained by biophysical, technical, and economic factors. Drawing on the results of Component A, the agricultural management options identified as effective and well proven for enhancing SOC stocks were used to estimate the achievable C sequestration potential in European agricultural mineral soils. For this, an area of implementation has been determined where the measures can be additionally implemented following a strict rule set. Then, two approaches were used to determine the C sequestration potential of each management option: (i) an estimation with the EFs created in component A, taking into account the results of component B spread out over the identified area of implementation and (ii) an estimation with the RothC model taking into account the improvements of the model achieved by component A and B. In addition, an economic evaluation of the management options was conducted. All of this has been conducted in a harmonized IPCC Tier 2 and Tier 3 Level II approach on European scale and for some countries and management options as well in a level III approach (Figure 2). For a case study in Italy, a policy evaluation was performed

estimating the effectiveness of CAP in increasing SOC by RothC simulations run at parcel level based on data provided by the Italian coordinator of paying agencies of the CAP.

Figure 3: CarboSeq approaches to estimate C sequestration potentials (dark boxes) and the GSOCseq approach of FAO (orange).

Area of implementation

The area of implementation for a measure to increase C accrual was defined based on biophysical, environmental and technical constraints as well as by economical constraints. For the CAP case study, the area of implementation corresponded to the actual application of Rural Development Programme measures by farmers. All measures are based on the same theoretical area of implementation which are agricultural mineral soils of Europe in the considered EJP SOIL countries (Figure 1) covering about 220 million hectares.

For each identified agricultural management option in Component A a strict rule set has been defined limiting this theoretical area of implementation to ensure that the option will be implemented additionally and in areas where it is possible and realistic based on pedo-environmental conditions (Seidel et al., 2024). For measures related to technical solutions (reduced and no tillage, irrigation, biochar) and crop rotations (cover crops, crop residue management) solely biophysical, environmental and technical constraints have been applied. For perennial legumes and temporary ley management, a possible scenario has been established following the goals of current EU policies on sustainable soil management where silage maize and maize for energy production has been replaced by perennial fodder crops and temporary ley management (COM, 2020). To limit the aerial extent of agroforestry, we followed the European Commission’s mid-term goal to “bring back at least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity features” where hedges and tree lines (as used in agroforestry) are such features (COM, 2020). Today, only two EU countries have reached the 10% target already – Malta and Cyprus, while all other EU countries are still below the 10% target. Thus, we developed an ambitious and a conservative scenario in which the 10% target will be reached through the implementation of agroforestry measures and hedges.

The identified potential area for implementing additional management options that boost C accrual is considerably higher in croplands than in grasslands. Potential C sequestration in grassland is restricted to the plantation of additional woody features like hedgerows and individual trees. Increased fertilisation for grasslands comes with high negative side effects and was therefore excluded as measure. In cropland, the largest areas of implementation are available for technical solutions

(tillage > biochar > irrigation) and improved crop rotations (cover crops > crop residues > perennial legumes and temporary ley management), while the area available for additional woody features is relatively small (Figure 4 **Error! Reference source not found.**). Besides the European area of implementation, country-specific areas for the individual management options have been identified as well (Seidel et al., 2024).

Figure 4: Agricultural management options ranked by total area of implementation in million hectares. Woody features contain hedge and tree rows on crop and grassland.

Estimation of the C sequestration potential

In a next step, these areas of implementation have been combined with the new European EFs calculated in component A (Panagea et al., 2023) to estimate a C sequestration potential for each measure in a Tier 2 level II approach (Figure 3). The results of the calculation showed that on European scale biochar application has by far the highest potential to increase soil C followed by woody features linked to agroforestry, tillage practices and only small total potentials with measures affecting crop rotations both in total amounts (Figure 5: Figure 5) as well as in yearly C sequestration potentials (Table 2) (Seidel et al., 2025 (in preparation)). Here, results of component B have been included where changes in N₂O emissions and subsoil C have been accounted for (Nikolaus and Lesschen, 2024; Parvin et al., 2024).

Figure 5: Agricultural management options ranked by total carbon sequestration potential in million Mg CO₂eq. “Woody features” contain hedge and tree rows on cropland and grassland.

Table 2: Overview of the studied agricultural management options and their additional C sequestration potential in million tonnes CO₂ equivalents per year. Increases and decreases in N₂O emissions and potential C sequestration through subsoils have been accounted for. C sequestration and N₂O emissions have been calculated over 50 years, except for biochar which was calculated over 100 years. From (Seidel et al., 2025, in preparation). ¹taken from Valkama et al. (2024) ²(Nikolaus and Lesschen, 2024)

Management option	Total additional C sequestration potential	Additional C sequestration potential	C sequestration changes considering N ₂ O emissions	C sequestration changes considering subsoils	Additional C sequestration potential considering N ₂ O emissions and subsoils
	[Mio t CO ₂ -eq]	[Mio t CO ₂ -eq a ⁻¹]			
Non-inversion tillage	446	8.9	-6.3	+2.6	5.2
Zero tillage	1574	31.5	-7.0	no data	-
Biochar	7703	77.0	~35% decrease in N ₂ O emissions expected ¹	0	-
Irrigation	140	2.8	no data	+0.8	-
Cover crops	208	4.2	-1.3	0	2.9
Crop residues	437	8.7	no data	+1.3	-
Perennial legumes, ley management	361	7.2	Reduction expected ²	+3.0	-
Woody features (conservative scenario)	97 (SOC)	38.8	+1.0	+1.3	41.1
	1106 (Biomass)				
	1203 (total)				
	380 (SOC)				
Woody features (ambitious scenario)	2647 (Biomass)	95.8	+2.3	+5.3	103.4
	3027 (total)				
Total conservative					
(not considering zero tillage and the ambitious woody vegetation scenario)	10847	148	141	157	150
Total ambitious					
(not considering non-inversion tillage and the conservative woody vegetation scenario)	13998	227	221.2	238	232

The Tier 2 level II approach for estimating C sequestration potentials across Europe highlighted the varying effectiveness of different management options to increase C accrual. Overall, our conservative estimated C sequestration potential of up to 148 million Mg CO₂eq per year corresponds to 32% of the current greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from European agriculture, including Norway, Switzerland, and Turkey (467.2 million Mg CO₂eq in 2020 (Statista Search Department, 2024a; FOEN, 2024; Statista Search Department, 2024b, 2024c, respectively) in the conservative scenario. In the ambitious scenario, the C sequestration potential corresponds to 227 million Mg CO₂eq per year or 49%. When adding the emissions of from peatlands under agricultural use reported in the Land Use, Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector of 236 Mg CO₂eq (Giersbergen et al., 2024, not including Turkey) our conservative C sequestration potential corresponds to 21% of agricultural GHG emissions and the ambitious scenario to 32%.

When including N₂O emissions of the four management options where there was data available, these potentials change to 141 million Mg CO₂eq per year and 221 million Mg CO₂eq per year for both scenarios respectively. This corresponds to 30 % and 47 % of the agricultural GHG emissions or when including the LULUCF sector to 20 % and 31 % respectively.

When including N₂O emissions and subsoil C effects of six management options where data was available, the conservative C sequestration potential is 150 million Mg CO₂eq per year corresponding to 32 % or when including the LULUCF sector to 21 % while the numbers for the ambitious scenario are 232 million Mg CO₂eq per year, 49 % and 33% respectively.

Overall, the three most efficient management options to mitigate climate change effects per implemented ha are the woody features, biochar application and perennial legumes and ley management outranking all other options (Table 3).

Table 3 Carbon (C) sequestration potential efficiency in tons CO₂ equivalents per hectare per year of agricultural management options taking N₂O emission changes and subsoil C changes into account

Management option	C sequestration potential	C sequestration potential including changes in N ₂ O emissions	C sequestration potential including changes in subsoil C	C sequestration potential including changes in N ₂ O emissions and subsoil C
Non-inversion tillage	5.1	4.8	6.6	6.3
No tillage	18.7	18.4	no data	-
Biochar	137.3	~35% decrease in N ₂ O emissions expected ¹	no data	-
Irrigation	10.5	no data	13.4	-
Cover crops	10.7	10.5	10.7	10.5
Crop residues	37.6	no data	43.5	-
Perennial legumes, temporary ley	66.4	Reduction expected ²	93.6	-
Woody features (ambitious)	365.2	366.1	419.2	420.2
Woody features (conservative)	347.9	348.8	381.5	382.4

Roth C EU model runs

As part of the CarboSeq project, the ModelToolBox was developed to enable harmonized and efficient simulations across partners with varying modelling expertise. This tool integrates multiple models and standardizes soil and crop management data flows using ontologies. Key models implemented include RothC and some of its variants, chosen for their relevance to European conditions. For the current purpose, 20-year simulations were run using climate data from 2000–2020, and a business-as-usual scenario was compared to SOC accrual scenarios to assess the potential of several changes of agricultural practices concerning crop residues (all incorporated to the soil vs all removed), cover crops (implemented were possible vs no cover crops) and ley rotations (increased frequency). The ModelToolBox is limited to annual arable crops and the crops included in such rotations. The current design is not compatible with perennial crops, whose management and subsequent impact on the carbon cycle is distinct.

A wide-ranging data set was meticulously assembled from existing literature, encompassing Europe (EU + United Kingdom, Switzerland, Norway and Turkey). Given the inherent diversity of climates and agricultural practices across the continent, a limited number of crop types and rotations were selected for analysis, based on published literature using LUCAS surveys and satellite imaging. This approach effectively encompassed two-thirds of the land area dedicated to agriculture on arable land.

At the European scale, the improvement of crop residues management on arable land could potentially lead to a C accrual of $0.14 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ on average and a total of 53 Mio $\text{MgCO}_2\text{eq a}^{-1}$ at EU scale. Entirely removing crop residues from the field would cause a release of 98 Mio $\text{MgCO}_2\text{eq a}^{-1}$ to the atmosphere. Further, a wider implementation of cover crops would allow an average C accrual of $0.58 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$ and a total of 224 Mio $\text{MgCO}_2\text{eq a}^{-1}$ at EU scale, while banishing cover crops would cause a release of 31 Mio $\text{MgCO}_2\text{eq a}^{-1}$.

The confidence in the proposed results is medium for improvement of crop residues management because of the lack of cross evaluations with other studies so far. Confidence for the extended implementation of cover crops is medium to low due to a possible over-estimation of the area of implementation of the measure. For increasing the leys frequencies in the rotations, a low confidence level is found which relates to the lack of pan-European estimates of C input for such plant systems within the proposed modelling framework.

National model runs of RothC

In addition, the partners were asked to run the simulations with their own national data sets which usually are higher in resolution and of better quality to compare these with the EU wide model runs. Out of all 10 partners who submitted reports, eight have run the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario and seven have run the sequestration scenarios.

The eight partners modelled trends in the BAU scenario that did not fit well to observed trends in soil inventories or to other modelling studies, according to the partners. For example, Estonia reported simulated SOC losses twice as high as in other SOC modelling approaches, Germany reported unrealistic SOC gains (even though SOC losses have been observed in soil inventory data), and Sweden and Slovakia reported unrealistic SOC losses (even though SOC gains have been observed in national soil inventories). This underlines the challenges in modelling the actual SOC trends or a business-as-usual scenario. However, these problems do not apply to the estimated C sequestration potentials that are derived from the difference on model runs.

For the sequestration potentials of the seven partners, the largest SOC gains were found in the biochar scenarios with $+28.2 \text{ t C /ha}$ on average. Adding more cover crops to the rotations led to $+4.7 \text{ t C /ha}$ on average, and leaving residues to the arable soils led to $+2.1 \text{ t C /ha}$ compared to removing them. SOC losses were found in the ley scenario where green maize was replaced with fodder legumes (-1.7 t C /ha) and in the No-residues scenario (-1.6 t C /ha). Removing existing Cover crops would lead to SOC losses of -0.9 t C/ha compared to the BAU scenario.

As the BAU scenarios differ from other studies and measured trends, the SOC changes in the sequestration scenarios should always be interpreted in relation to the BAU scenario as has been done above and not misinterpreted as forecast.

Comparison of RothC with other models

In addition to employing a single model to evaluate C dynamics in soil, an intercomparison of four distinct models (model ensemble) was undertaken. The research focuses on assessing SOC models in agricultural systems, with particular attention to the role of real crop rotation practices and including the spatial dimension in the evaluation through a multi-step analysis. Conducted in the Foggia Province of southern Italy, the study incorporates spatialisation at each stage of the protocol. By combining crop rotation practices, an advanced multi-step methodology, including a spatialised analysis, increased the capacity of the model ensemble to mimic the real data and represent an advancement and refinement of SOC modelling approaches (Andrenelli et al., 2025).

The RothC simulation applied to the CAP, in the Italian case study, suggests that both conservative agriculture and the combination of cover crops, crop rotations and burial of plant residues (referred to as “environmentally sustainable management methods”) have a positive impact on SOC by reducing C losses or even achieving C sequestration (Criscuoli et al., 2024). It is important to recognize that each agricultural management option comes with distinct synergies and trade-offs, in addition to its impact on SOC which cannot be forgotten.

Root-Shoot database

A literature and data compilation on belowground and above ground biomass of different crops was conducted in order to improve allometric functions that are used with the RothC model or others to model SOC trends under different management options. The root shoot database is a collection of data taken from published peer reviewed literature gathered over the space of a year covering studies up until the end of 2022. Strict criteria were used for inclusion in the database. The study should include root and shoot estimates and/or root shoot ratios. The studies should be within Europe and contain a minimum of meta data. We also required that the studies were based on field measurements and not pot studies. A total of 23 studies were identified as meeting the criteria for inclusion in the database resulting in 451 individual measurements across 11 countries in Europe (including the UK). Although the initial goal of the project was to provide data on a range of perennial and annual crops it was discovered that most of the relevant studies were focused on a few crops. Most notably the database was dominated by measurements of wheat cropping systems with a smaller proportion of measurements for barley and maize. There was a distinct lack of studies for cropping systems examining root crops or perennial crops. A detailed analysis of the root shoot database was undertaken both within this project and as part of the MaxRootC project. General findings from the construction and analysis of the Root-Shoot database showed that there were significant challenges in the variability and quality of the data available in the literature, that posed significant challenges to the application of the database in the formation of new allometric functions. Due to high variability, the data appear best interpreted using simple allometric approaches, such as a fixed root-shoot ratio per species. A key finding from the analysis was the need for standardised approaches to quantify root parameters to provide more effective data for comparison at national, international and global scales.

Economical evaluation of the measures

An economic assessment of a number of the carbon sequestration measures was undertaken based on cost-effectiveness criteria. The cost of each measure was assessed at EU scale and for a number of countries (Republic of Ireland, Germany, Norway and Czech Republic) where full cost data was available. Cost results are presented on a per hectare average basis and on an aggregate basis (accounting for relevant areas of implementation). Cost estimates were applied to carbon sequestration potentials derived through the project to generate a cost-effectiveness estimate (€ per Mg of CO₂e sequestered) for each measure. At the EU scale, results indicate that a limited number of measures meet the cost-effectiveness criteria based on a shadow price of carbon of 89 € per Mg CO₂e⁻¹. The cost-effective measures at the EU scale were silvopasture, alley-cropping and hedges on grass and cropland. A similar finding prevailed across the countries examined; however, the cost-effectiveness rankings did not remain consistent as the cost of certain measures varied across countries, which impacted cost-effectiveness.

Key results and research gaps

1. Carbon loss mitigation is the precondition for carbon sequestration. Agricultural carbon sequestration measures can compensate for greenhouse gas emissions only if the accrual of soil carbon is larger than the loss under business-as-usual conditions (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Carbon (C) loss mitigation or C sequestration? Taken from (Don et al., 2024).

2. In the CarboSeq project 27 research institutions across Europe worked on estimating a realistic, feasible carbon sequestration potential of European agriculture, that is beyond existing theoretical potentials.

3. There is a significant feasible potential to contribute with agricultural management options to climate change mitigation through carbon accumulation in soils and biomass. This technical and feasible C sequestration potential corresponds to 20% of current EU agricultural greenhouse gas emissions (sector agriculture and agricultural emissions sector LULUCF) when including biochar application and reduces to 10% when not including biochar.
4. Changes in agricultural management in order to sequester carbon have multiple side effects and co-benefits, depending on soil type, climate and farm conditions. Increasing soil organic carbon is more than just climate change mitigation. It is key to increase soil health, crucial for sustainable agriculture and helps to increase resilience of agriculture to adapt to climate change.
5. European cropland soils show much larger potential for carbon sequestration than grassland soils.
6. The success of carbon sequestration efforts in European agriculture hinges on scaling up the area where agricultural measures are implemented. Even if the carbon sequestration per hectare of a measure is low, the impact is high when it is applied on a large area. Implementing these measures needs political ambition and economic incentives that play a crucial role in turning potential carbon sequestration into realized outcomes.
7. All measures that we analysed showed on average a net climate mitigation effect also when taking tradeoffs with increased non-CO₂ greenhouse gases and indirect effects (e.g. changes in fuel consumption, fertilizer or herbicide needs) into account.
8. Effects of carbon sequestration measures are significantly underestimated by up to 50 % (measure dependent) when considering only the topsoil down to 30 cm soil depth. Carbon farming schemes and carbon monitoring should be extended to at least 50 cm soil depth.
9. Perennial fodder legumes increase carbon in soils, but annual legumes do not compared to common annual crops.
10. Agroforestry with hedges, alley cropping and silvopasture on agricultural land have a large carbon sequestration potential in almost all countries with most additional carbon stored in the biomass. At the same time, they have the highest sequestration efficiency per ha implemented and multiple positive co-benefits, such as increasing biodiversity and supplying additional woody feedstock (e.g., for biochar). This comes with a trade-off for a reduced arable area where food can be produced.
11. Crop residues are important to maintain soil carbon. In Europe most crop residuals are returned to the soil directly or with farmyard manure. If straw biomass would be removed (e.g. as fibre for renewable biobased products) and not returned to the field, carbon losses are to be expected.

12. 40% of the carbon in the biomass used to produce biochar can be stabilised on the long-term through pyrolysis. The potential of biochar is constrained by costs, feedstock availability and competition on different utilisation pathways of feedstock.
13. With the newly developed version of the soil organic carbon model RothC we can model the effects of biochar on soil organic carbon.
14. New research gaps were discovered during the project:
 - Not enough long-term field experiments on crop rotation effects, land-use changes and grassland management
 - Not enough data from long-term experiments on management effects on subsoil carbon stocks
 - Missing research sites and long-term experiments on water-logged mineral soils
 - Insufficient data in high resolution on crop management and thus carbon input at European scale, especially in perennial systems (grasslands, ley-rotation, agroforestry, silvopasture)
 - Missing data on current use of exogenous organic matter in European agriculture (type, amount, location)
 - Poorly constrained business-as-usual scenario of agricultural soil organic carbon dynamics under current management in Europe due to missing management data
 - Insufficient data on effects of no tillage on above and belowground biomass and yield

Publications linked to Carboseq:

Barančíková, G., Koco, Š., Halas, J., Takáč, J., Makovníková, J., & Kizeková, M. (2024). Modelling of soil organic carbon dynamic on grassland under different management and climate scenarios.

<https://doi.org/10.2478/agri-2023-0009>

Don, A., Seidel, F., Leifeld, J., Kätterer, T., Martin, M., Pellerin, S., Emde, D., Seitz, D., & Chenu, C. (2023). Carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation—Definitions and pitfalls. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16983>

Don, A., Seidel, F., Leifeld, J., Kätterer, T., Martin, M., Pellerin, S., Emde, D., Seitz, D., & Chenu, C. (2024). Reply letter to Munoz et al. 'on the importance of time in carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation'—Keep carbon sequestration terminologies consistent and functional. In Global Change Biology (Bd. 30, Nummer 3).

<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17230>

Emde, D., Poeplau, C., Don, A., Heilek, S., & Schneider, F. (2024). The centennial legacy of land-use change on organic carbon stocks of German agricultural soils. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17444>

Fohrafellner J., Zechmeister-Boltenstern S., Murugan R., Keiblinger K., Spiegel H., Valkama E. (2023). Meta-analysis protocol on the effects of cover crops on pool specific soil organic carbon. *MethodsX*, 11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2023.102411>.

Fulu Tao, Taru Palosuo, Aleksii Lehtonen, Jaakko Heikkinen, & Raisa Mäkipää. (2023). Soil organic carbon sequestration potential for croplands in Finland over 2021–2040 under the interactive impacts of climate change and agricultural management. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103671>

Gabriela, B., Štefan, K., Jarmila, M., Skalsky, R., & Kobza, J. (2023). Development of soil organic carbon stock on agricultural soils of Slovakia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10213125>

Gabriela, B., & Koco, Š. (2023). Soil organic carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils in Europe (CarboSeq). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10416993>

Harbo L.S., Olesen J.E., Liang Z., Christensen B.T., Elsgaard L. (2022). Estimating organic carbon stocks of mineral soils in Denmark: Impact of bulk density and content of rock fragments. *Geoderma Regional* (30). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2022.e00560>.

Harbo, L., Olesen, J. E., Lemming, C., Christensen, B. T., & Elsgaard, L. (2023). Limitations of farm management data in analyses of decadal changes in SOC stocks in the Danish soil-monitoring network. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13379>

Hugenschmidt, J., & Kay, S. (2023). Unmasking adaption of tree root structure in agroforestry Systems in Switzerland using GPR. *Geoderma Regional*, 34(e00659), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2023.e00659>

Koco, Š., Barančíkova, G., Kobza, J., & Halas, J. (2024). Preparation of a Soil Data Database for Modelling Soil Organic Carbon Stocks on Agricultural Soils in Slovakia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559244>

Leifeld, J. (2023). The importance of biochar quality and pyrolysis yield for soil carbon sequestration in practice. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13396>

Leifeld, J., Hardy, B., Budai, A., Elsgaard, L., Keel, S. G., Levavasseur, F., Liang, Z., Mondini, C., Plaza, C., & Rodrigues, L. (2024a). Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046237>

Liang Z., Rasmussen J., Poeplau C., Elsgaard L. (2023). Priming effects decrease with the quantity of cover crop residues – Potential implications for soil carbon sequestration. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2023.109110>.

Martín-Lammerding, D., Gabriel, J. L., Zambrana, E., Santín-Montanyá, I., & Tenorio, J. L. (2021). Organic Amendment vs. Mineral Fertilization under Minimum Tillage: Changes in Soil Nutrients, Soil Organic Matter, Biological Properties and Yield after 10 Years. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11080700>

Meurer, K. H. E., Hendriks, C. M. J., Faber, J. H., Kuikman, P. J., van Egmond, F., Garland, G., Putku, E., Barancikova, G., Makovniková, J., Chenu, C., Herrmann, A. M., & Bispo, A. (2024). How does national

SOC monitoring on agricultural soils align with the EU strategies? An example using five case studies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(2), e13477. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13477>

Mockevičienė, I. (2023). The Response of Retisol's Carbon Storage Potential to Various Organic Matter Inputs. In *Sustainability* (Bd. 15, Nummer 15). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151511495>

Rodrigues, L., Hardy, B., Huyghebeert, B., Fohrafellner, J., Fornara, D., Barančíková, G., Bárcena, T., De Boever, M., Di Bene, C., Feizienė, D., Kätterer, T., Laszlo, P., O'Sullivan, L., Seitz, D., & Leifeld, J. (2021). Achievable agricultural soil carbon sequestration across Europe from country-specific estimates. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15897>

Schneider, F., Poeplau, C., & Don, A. (2021). Predicting ecosystem responses by data-driven reciprocal modelling. *Global Change Biology*, 27(21), 5670–5679. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15817>

Seitz, D., Fischer, L. M., Dechow, R., Wiesmeier, M., & Don, A. (2022). The potential of cover crops to increase soil organic carbon. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-022-05438-w>

Skalsky, R., Barančíková, G., Makovnikova, J., Koco, Š., Halas, J., & Kobza, J. (2024). Regional topsoil organic carbon content in the agricultural soils of Slovakia and its drivers, as revealed by the most recent national soil monitoring data. *Environmental Challenges* 14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2023.100816>

Štefan, K., Skalsky, R., Gabriela, B., & Bezák, P. (2023). National contribution of Slovakia to the global soil organic carbon sequestration potential map. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10213187>

Zhang H.-M., Liang Z., Li Y., Chen Z.-X., Zhang J.-B., Cai Z.-C., Elsgaard L., Cheng Y., van Groenigen K.J., Abalos D. (2022). Liming modifies greenhouse gas fluxes from soils: A meta-analysis of biological drivers. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108182>.

Data sets and tools linked to CarboSeq

Blanchy, G., D'Hose, T., De Boever, M., Keiblinger, K., Spiegel, H., Sandén, T., Alvaro-Fuentes, J., Kay, S., Seidel, F., Don, A., & Ruysschaert, G. (2023). EJPSOIL CarboSeq crop and soil management database template. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8094887>

Blanchy, G. (2022). Export module of the EJP SOIL CarboSeq WP2 database (0.6.5). Zenodo. [tool] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7415077>

G. Bárcena, T., Weldon, S., Inagaki, T., Hansdotter, S., & Daniel, R. (2024). Root Shoot Database [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242897>

Holland, J., Klumpp, K., & Gordon, A. (2024). Grassland database WP4 CarboSeq [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515034>

Leifeld, J., Hardy, B., Budai, A., Elsgaard, L., Keel, S. G., Levavasseur, F., Liang, Z., Mondini, C., Plaza, C., & Rodrigues, L. (2024b). New parameter estimates for exogenous organic materials including biochar for the Rothamsted carbon model [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12582998>

Parisse Barbara, Alilla Roberta, & De Natale Flora. (2023). EJP SOIL CarboSeq agrometeorological datasets (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399180>

Poeplau, C. (2023). Dataset of manuscript "No detectable upper limit of mineral associated carbon in temperate agricultural soils" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966076>

Poeplau, C. (2024). Dataset for "Towards an ecosystem capacity to stabilise organic carbon in soils" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12801430>

Ruyschaert, G., Panagea, I., Blanchy, G., Keiblinger, K., Diacono, M., Rosinger, C., Di Bene, C., Makoschitz, L., Sandén, T., Spiegel, H., Alonso-Ayuso, M., Martinez-Garcia, L. B., Alvaro-Fuentes, J., Suhadolc, M., Ocvirk, K., Kay, S., Viaud, V., Bárcena, T. G., Bruno, A., ... Don, A. (2023). EJP SOIL CarboSeq crop and soil management database (2023_07_07) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8130195>

Schneider, F., Poeplau, C., & Don, A. (2021). Predicting ecosystem responses by data-driven reciprocal modelling. Global Change Biology. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5171794>

Tommaso Tadiello, Marco Acutis, Alessia Perego, Calogero Schillaci, & Elena Valkama. (2022). Databases to: Soil Organic Carbon Under Conservation Agriculture In Mediterranean And Humid Subtropical Climates: Global Meta-Analysis. [Data set] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7404592>

Selected meaningful deliverables linked to CarboSeq

D#WP1.5: Final report of CarboSeq

D#WP2.1: Report on emission factors of each measure (effects on SOC stocks). <https://zenodo.org/records/14045964>

D#WP2.2, D#WP2.3, D#WP8.1, D#WP8.3, D#WP8.4: Report on the area of implementation of selected agricultural measures, their definitions and the calculation of the tier 2 C sequestration potential. <https://zenodo.org/records/14046100>

D#WP3.1, D#WP3.2, D#WP3.3, D#WP3.4, D#WP3.5: Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments. <https://zenodo.org/records/14046237>

D#WP4.1: Report on rates of soil carbon accumulation across European grasslands. <https://zenodo.org/records/14258009>

D#WP4.2: Method to estimate C inputs and model SOC- sequestration measures on grasslands. <https://zenodo.org/records/14258056>

D#WP4.3: Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP8. <https://zenodo.org/records/14258166>

D#WP4.4: C-input rates for grassland measures. <https://zenodo.org/records/14258227>

D#WP4.5: Estimates of C input rates using LUCAS data for European grasslands.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14603609>

D#WP5.1: Literature review and meta-analysis on N₂O emissions related to agricultural SOC-sequestration measures. <https://zenodo.org/records/14633996>

D#WP5.2: Open-source database of N₂O emissions related to SOC-sequestration measures.

<https://zenodo.org/records/14046545>

D#WP5.3: Assessment of SOC-sequestration measures on other GHG emissions.

<https://zenodo.org/records/14506063>

D#WP6.1: Effect of agricultural management practices on subsoil organic carbon content - a meta-analysis for warm temperate and snow climate zones. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14196741>

D#WP8.2: Economic analysis of carbon sequestration measures.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14622481>

D#WP9.1: Compiled default dataset of spatially explicit climate, soil, and EU management at European level for the model runs. <https://zenodo.org/records/8399180>

D#WP9.2: Root to Shoot database. <https://zenodo.org/records/14242897>

D#WP9.6: Report on the assessment of the European potential SOC-sequestration, and assessment of areas where SOC losses should be prevented in Europe. <https://zenodo.org/records/14631518>

D#WP9.7: Web platform with an interactive SOC-sequestration potential map.

<https://shinyapp.cra.wallonie.be/ejpsoil-carboseq>

D#WP9.8: SOC sequestration potential assessment of CAP measures and irrigation techniques.

<https://zenodo.org/records/14505060>

References

- Andrenelli, M.C., Bellocchi, G., Di Bene, C., Ferchaud, F., Napoli, R., Raynal, H., Farina, R., 2025. Enhancing soil organic carbon modelling in agricultural systems: A spatially dynamic multi-model ensemble in Southern Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609796>
- Blanchy, G., D'Hose, T., Donmez, C., Hoffmann, C., Makoschitz, L., Murugan, R., O'Sullivan, L., Sandén, T., Spiegel, A., Svoboda, N., Zechmeister-Boltenstern, S., Klumpp, K., 2023. EJP MTE/LTE metadataset v1.0.1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7598122>
- Bolinder, M.A., Crotty, F., Elsen, A., Frac, M., Kismányoky, T., Lipiec, J., Tits, M., Tóth, Z., Kätterer, T., 2020. The effect of crop residues, cover crops, manures and nitrogen fertilization on soil organic carbon changes in agroecosystems: a synthesis of reviews. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Change* 25, 929–952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-020-09916-3>
- Börjesson, G., Bolinder, M.A., Kirchmann, H., Kätterer, T., 2018. Organic carbon stocks in topsoil and subsoil in long-term ley and cereal monoculture rotations. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 54, 549–558. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-018-1281-x>
- Chenu, C., Angers, D.A., Barré, P., Derrien, D., Arrouays, D., Balesdent, J., 2019. Increasing organic stocks in agricultural soils: Knowledge gaps and potential innovations. *Soil Tillage Res.* 188, 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2018.04.011>
- COM, 2020. EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives, Brussels.

- Criscuoli, I., Falconi, I., Andrenelli, M.C., Farina, R., Galioto, F., Fantappiè, M., Martelli, A., Varia, F., Lasorella, M.V., Guccione, G.D., 2024. SOC sequestration potential assessment of CAP measures. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14505060>
- Don, A., Seidel, F., Leifeld, J., Kätterer, T., Martin, M., Pellerin, S., Emde, D., Seitz, D., Chenu, C., 2024. Carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation—Definitions and pitfalls. *Glob. Change Biol.* 30, e16983. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16983>
- Drexler, S., Gensior, A., Don, A., 2021. Carbon sequestration in hedgerow biomass and soil in the temperate climate zone. *Reg. Environ. Change* 21, 74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01798-8>
- Emde, D., Hannam, K.D., Most, I., Nelson, L.M., Jones, M.D., 2021. Soil organic carbon in irrigated agricultural systems: A meta-analysis. *Glob. Change Biol.* 27, 3898–3910. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15680>
- Fetting, C., 2020. THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL.
- FOEN, F.O. for the E., 2024. Latest greenhouse gas inventory of Switzerland [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/themen/thema-klima/klima--daten--indikatoren-und-karten/daten--treibhausgasemissionen-der-schweiz/swiss-climate-reporting-under-the-unfccc/swiss-greenhouse-gas-inventories/swiss-greenhouse-gas-inventory-1990-2013.html> (accessed 8.1.24).
- Giersbergen, Q., Barthelmes, A., Couwenberg, John, Fritz, C., Lång, K., Martin, N., Tanneberger, F., 2024. Identifying hotspots of greenhouse gas emissions from drained peatlands in the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4629642/v1>
- Holland, J., Klumpp, K., Gordon, A., 2024a. Grassland database WP4 CarboSeq. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14515034>
- Holland, J., Klumpp, K., Martin, M., Gordon, A., 2024b. Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14258166>
- IPCC, ., Buendia, E.C., Guendehou, S., Limmeechokchai, B., Pipatti, R., Rojas, Y., Sturgiss, R., Tanabe, K., Wirth, T., Romano, D., Witi, J., Garg, A., Weitz, M.M., Cai, B., Ottinger, D.A., Dong, H., MacDonal, J.D., Ogle, S.M., Rocha, M.T., Sanz Sanchez, M.J., Bartram, D.M., Towprayoon, S., 2019. 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/index.html> (accessed 8.1.24).
- Jenkinson, D.S., Coleman, K., 2008. The turnover of organic carbon in subsoils. Part 2. Modelling carbon turnover. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 59, 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2008.01026.x>
- Kätterer, T., Börjesson, G., Kirchmann, H., 2014. Changes in organic carbon in topsoil and subsoil and microbial community composition caused by repeated additions of organic amendments and N fertilisation in a long-term field experiment in Sweden. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 189, 110–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.03.025>
- Keel, S.G., Bretscher, D., Leifeld, J., von Ow, A., Wüst-Galley, C., 2023. Soil carbon sequestration potential bounded by population growth, land availability, food production, and climate change. *Carbon Manag.* 14, 2244456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2023.2244456>
- Keesstra, S.D., Chenu, C., Munkholm, L.J., Cornu, S., Kuikman, P.J., Thorsøe, M.H., Besse-Lototskaya, A., Visser, S.M., 2024. European agricultural soil management: Towards climate-smart and sustainability, knowledge needs and research approaches. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13437. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13437>
- Klumpp, K., Holland, J., 2024. Report on rates of soil carbon accumulation across European grasslands.
- Leifeld, J., Hardy, B., Budai, A., Elsgaard, L., Keel, S.G., Levvasseur, F., Liang, Z., Mondini, C., Plaza, C., Rodrigues, L., 2024a. Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046237>

- Leifeld, J., Hardy, B., Budai, A., Elsgaard, L., Keel, S.G., Levvasseur, F., Liang, Z., Mondini, C., Plaza, C., Rodrigues, L., 2024b. New parameter estimates for exogenous organic materials including biochar for the Rothamsted carbon model. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12582998>
- Li, C., Frohling, S., Butterbach-Bahl, K., 2005. Carbon Sequestration in Arable Soils is Likely to Increase Nitrous Oxide Emissions, Offsetting Reductions in Climate Radiative Forcing. *Clim. Change* 72, 321–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-005-6791-5>
- Lorenz, K., Lal, R., 2005. The Depth Distribution of Soil Organic Carbon in Relation to Land Use and Management and the Potential of Carbon Sequestration in Subsoil Horizons, in: *Advances in Agronomy*. Academic Press, pp. 35–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(05\)88002-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(05)88002-2)
- Lugato, E., Leip, A., Jones, A., 2018. Mitigation potential of soil carbon management overestimated by neglecting N₂O emissions. *Nat. Clim. Change* 8, 219–223. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0087-z>
- Menichetti, L., Ekblad, A., Kätterer, T., 2015. Contribution of roots and amendments to soil carbon accumulation within the soil profile in a long-term field experiment in Sweden. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 200, 79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.11.003>
- Meurer, K.H.E., Haddaway, N.R., Bolinder, M.A., Kätterer, T., 2018. Tillage intensity affects total SOC stocks in boreo-temperate regions only in the topsoil—A systematic review using an ESM approach. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* 177, 613–622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2017.12.015>
- Minasny, B., Malone, B.P., McBratney, A.B., Angers, D.A., Arrouays, D., Chambers, A., Chaplot, V., Chen, Z.-S., Cheng, K., Das, B.S., Field, D.J., Gimona, A., Hedley, C.B., Hong, S.Y., Mandal, B., Marchant, B.P., Martin, M., McConkey, B.G., Mulder, V.L., O'Rourke, S., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Odeh, I., Padarian, J., Paustian, K., Pan, G., Poggio, L., Savin, I., Stolbovoy, V., Stockmann, U., Sulaeman, Y., Tsui, C.-C., Vågen, T.-G., Van Wesemael, B., Winowiecki, L., 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002>
- Morari, F., Berti, A., Dal Ferro, N., Piccoli, I., 2019. Deep Carbon Sequestration in Cropping Systems, in: Lal, R., Francaviglia, R. (Eds.), *Sustainable Agriculture Reviews 29: Sustainable Soil Management: Preventive and Ameliorative Strategies*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 33–65. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-26265-5_2
- Nikolaus, K., Lesschen, J.P., 2024. Assessment of SOC sequestration measures on other GHG emissions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14506063>
- Panagea, I., Blanchy, G., Keiblinger, K., Diacono, M., Rosinger, C., Quataert, P., Di Bene, C., Göttinger, S., Makoschitz, L., Sandén, T., Spiegel, H., Alonso-Ayuso, M., Martinez-Garcia, L., Álvaro-, J., Suhaldolc, M., Ocvirk, K., Kay, S., Viaud, V., Drexler, S., Seidel, F., Don, A., Ruyschaert, G., 2023. EJP SOIL-CarboSeq, D2.1, Report on emission factors (effects on SOC stocks) of each measure.
- Panagea, I.S., Quataert, P., Alonso-Ayuso, M., Bárcena, T.G., De Boever, M., Diacono, M., Jacobs, A., Jensen, J.L., Seidel, F., Seitz, D., Spiegel, H., Vanden Nest, T., Don, A., Ruyschaert, G., 2025. Forage legumes in crop rotation increase soil organic carbon stocks – Evidence from 21 European long-term field experiments.
- Parvin, N., Kätterer, T., Sierra, C.A., Skadell, L., Don, A., Bolinder, M.A., 2024. Effect of agricultural management practices on subsoil organic carbon content - a meta-analysis for boreo-temperate climates. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14196741>
- Poeplau, C., Don, A., 2015. Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils via cultivation of cover crops – A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 200, 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.10.024>
- Porre, R., Martinez-Garcia, L.B., Diaz-Pines, E., Esparza-Robles, U.R., Lesschen, J.P., 2026. Literature review and meta-analysis on N₂O emissions related to agricultural SOC-sequestration measures.

- Rodrigues, L., Budai, A., Elsgaard, L., Hardy, B., Keel, S.G., Mondini, C., Plaza, C., Leifeld, J., 2023. The importance of biochar quality and pyrolysis yield for soil carbon sequestration in practice. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 74, e13396. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13396>
- Ruyschaert, G., Panagea, I., Blanchy, G., Keiblinger, K., Diacono, M., Rosinger, C., Di Bene, C., Makoschitz, L., Sandén, T., Spiegel, H., Alonso-Ayuso, M., Martinez-Garcia, L.B., Alvaro-Fuentes, J., Suhadolc, M., Ocvirk, K., Kay, S., Viaud, V., Bárcena, T.G., Bruno, A., Carranca, C., Castanheira, N., De Boever, M., Demir, Z., D'Hose, T., Erdal, Ü., Feiza, V., Gabriel, J.L., Ghiasi, S., Gillikin, A., Hirte, J., Hendriks, C., Jacobs, A., Jensen, J.L., Kauer, K., Mertens, K., Mihelič, R., Mockeviciene, I., Pardon, P., Parvin, N., Pfeil, C., Plaza, C., Santín-Montanyá, M.I., Schneider, F., Seitz, D., Vanino, S., Verdonk, L., Vilkiene, M., Seidel, F., Don, A., 2023. EJPSOIL CarboSeq crop and soil management database. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8130195>
- Seidel, F., Schneider, F., Don, A., and more, 2025. Estimating a feasible carbon sequestration potential of European agricultural mineral soils through optimized agricultural management. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046100>
- Seidel, F., Schneider, F., Seitz, D., Don, A., 2024. Report on the area of implementation of selected agricultural measures, their definitions and the calculation of the tier 2 C sequestration potential. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046100>
- Sierra, C.A., Ahrens, B., Bolinder, M.A., Braakhekke, M.C., von Fromm, S., Kätterer, T., Luo, Z., Parvin, N., Wang, G., 2024. Carbon sequestration in the subsoil and the time required to stabilize carbon for climate change mitigation. *Glob. Change Biol.* 30, e17153. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17153>
- Statista Search Department, S., 2024a. EU-28: annual greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture 2022 [WWW Document]. Statista. URL <https://www.statista.com/statistics/879954/annual-greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-agriculture-in-european-union/> (accessed 8.1.24).
- Statista Search Department, S., 2024b. Norway: annual greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture 2022 [WWW Document]. Statista. URL <https://www.statista.com/statistics/689622/annual-greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-agriculture-in-norway/> (accessed 8.1.24).
- Statista Search Department, S., 2024c. Turkey: annual greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture 2020 [WWW Document]. Statista. URL <https://www.statista.com/statistics/689630/annual-greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-agriculture-in-turkey/> (accessed 8.1.24).
- Trost, B., Prochnow, A., Drastig, K., Meyer-Aurich, A., Ellmer, F., Baumecker, M., 2013. Irrigation, soil organic carbon and N₂O emissions. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 33, 733–749. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-013-0134-0>
- Valkama, E., Tzemi, D., Esparza-Robles, U.R., Syp, A., O'Toole, A., Maenhout, P., 2024. Effectiveness of soil management strategies for mitigation of NO emissions in European arable land: A meta-analysis. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13488. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13488>

